

Review of effects of weather extremes on soil biota

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1. Introduction

Climate change not only involves a gradual increase in average global temperature in the longer term but also is about the increasing occurrence of various extreme weather events. Both aspects may affect soil biodiversity. This chapter deals with the effect of extreme weather events on soil fauna in the short term.

Weather extremes, such as floods, droughts, and cold spells have shaped ecosystems and organisms for millennia (Grant et al., 2017). However, the Earth is currently experiencing an unprecedented period of anthropogenic disturbances, and climate models predict increased intensity and frequency of weather extremes (IPCC, 2014). By definition, extreme events exceed the norms of environmental conditions and therefore drive significant mortality, resulting in range shifts, local extinctions, and transitions to novel ecosystem states (Harris et al., 2018). While sporadic extreme events can promote biodiversity and increase population resilience (Coleman & Wernberg, 2020), the increasing frequency of extreme events over the last three decades (60% increase in Europe, EASAC, 2013), threatens ecological, social and economic stability. Due to climate change, the most significant changes are observed in the amount of precipitations and the duration of droughts, but air temperatures are also rising, and heat-wave events have become more frequent (Tabari, 2020). These events are not independent, as global warming intensifies the risk of floods and droughts (Asadieh & Krakauer, 2017) and freeze-thaw cycles in winter and early spring, which can be destructive to agriculture.

Although extreme weather events are fairly well investigated in plant community ecology, much less effort has been made in soil ecology to study this aspect of climate change. Further, despite the documented importance of soil organisms on ecosystem functioning (Bardgett & van der Putten, 2014), even less attention has been given to soil ecological responses. Here we present a focused review of soil fauna responses to major classes of weather extreme events affecting agroecosystems in Europe (Devot et al., 2023), including drought, heavy rainfalls and freeze-thaw cycles (Figure 1). Heat-waves, driven by rising global temperatures, rapidly dry out soils and are most harmful to soil when not accompanied by rainfalls or when leading to a reduction in snow cover over winter which leads to soil freezing. As the effects of heatwaves on soil fauna is intricately tied to soil moisture, disentangling the effects of soil warming and soil moisture is difficult. Heat-wave effects on soil biota are therefore presented either under drought or freeze-thaw cycles in this review. Fires are devastating extreme events, particularly in forest habitats, and their impact on soil ecosystems has been well documented elsewhere (Agbeshie et al., 2022; Certini et al., 2021). Many environmental factors interact and affect soil organisms, and disentangling the influence of these factors can be extremely challenging. While tackling the effect of multiple stressors is outside of the scope of this review, it is important to be aware that stressors often interact and potentially exacerbate the overall impact on soil communities (Rillig et al., 2019).

For each extreme weather event type, we qualitatively review the available literature for effects on four major soil fauna groups: microbes (bacteria and fungi), nematodes, collembolans and earthworms. These groups have been widely investigated and are often used as soil biotic indicators in soil health (Faber et al., 2022; Rutgers et al., 2008).

Figure 1. Spatial and temporal variation in extreme weather events, and their major expected impact on soil physical and chemical properties. Images from [EcoWatch](#), [Euractiv](#) and [Grain Central](#).

2. Extreme weather description

a. Drought

Drought is a prolonged period of abnormally low precipitation. Water content in the upper soil layers is usually reduced relatively quickly, but deeper soil layers (30-100 cm) may not be immediately affected (Buitink et al., 2020). The rate at which soil dries will depend on the type and amount of soil and vegetation cover. Lower soil water content increases soil hardness and shrinkage and reduces water films making movements for many soil organisms more difficult. Unlike floods, which can occur over the course of hours and quickly inundate areas, droughts manifest more slowly in the soil environment. As such, soil organisms may have the capacity to move to more favorable microhabitats or enter some state of metabolic inactivity in order to avoid desiccation.

b. Heavy rainfall

Heavy rainfall can result in waterlogging, which compacts the topsoil with water, disrupting aggregates, and filling up soil pores with water, limiting aeration. Increased moisture is associated with increased nutrient leaching and reduced oxygen diffusion in the soil (Freeman et al., 2004). The oxygen concentration in waterlogged soils is significantly reduced after 24h (Banach et al., 2009). The availability of micro- and macro-elements in poorly oxygenated soils can be two to four times lower. This means that soil organisms have higher energy expenditure and need to be phenotypically and/or genetically adapted to survive longer periods of waterlogging.

a. Freeze-thaw cycles

Freeze-thaw cycles are by far the least investigated extreme event investigated in this review (Figure 1-4), likely due to the difficulty to assess it in the field. Freeze-thaw cycles can cause soil to crack and heave, which can cause loss of soil structure and erosion. To survive under frost conditions soil biota basically have to be able to cope with limited availability of free water, i.e. coping with increasing salt concentrations that disrupt cell physiology and induce osmotic disturbance. Thawing often results in rapid nutrient release, especially nitrogen, as microbial communities become more active. However, this nutrient release can lead to leaching, particularly in soils that are still saturated after snowmelt or rain events whilst plant growth is still neglectable. The increasing frequency of freeze-thaw cycles might make it more difficult for soil biota to adapt and respond, as it requires energy to produce anti-freezing proteins or other coping metabolites, and the regulation of the production and disassembly of such metabolites becomes increasingly difficult to attune.

3. Material and methods

The literature search was performed on 10 October 2024 in ISI Web of Science. We performed four separate searches for each soil fauna indicator group (microbes, nematodes, micro-arthropods, and earthworms) in combination with a search string for extreme weather events relating to drought, floods and freeze-thaw cycles and a search string for habitat type, including cropland and grassland. Forests were excluded from this review as soil fauna in these habitats generally respond differently to extreme events (Blankinship et al., 2011a; Heiniger et al., 2015; Moreno et al., 2019). The search was applied to abstract, title and keywords, except for microbes where we limited the search to the title as to avoid too many hits. In addition, papers were filtered to exclude book chapters, conference papers and pre-prints. Finally, we refined the search to limit the papers to relevant ISI Web of Science categories. For a summary of the search terms see Table 1. All papers were scanned, and for each paper we recorded the taxon studied, the extreme event investigated (drought/water stress, flood/waterlogging/extreme precipitation, freeze-thaw cycles) the habitat (grassland (including pastures, meadows, heathlands as well as floodplains for earthworms), agriculture (including annual crops and agroforestry), the experimental set up (field, mesocosm), the indicator used (e.g. abundance, richness) and the direction of the effect (positive, negative, no effect).

Table 1. Search terms used per category of papers and studies per soil fauna group before and after abstract/paper check. *All searches were applied to topic searcher (TS, including abstract, keywords and titles) except for microbes where search was applied to Title for the extreme weather event string, not doing this would have results in a selection of 2396 papers.

Group	Screened papers	Studies	Entries	Search string
Earthworms	206	43	49	"earthworm*" OR "annelida" OR "lumbricidae"
Mesofauna	322	30	68	"collembolas" OR "collembola" OR "collembolans" OR "springtail" OR "springtails" OR "mite*" OR "acari" OR "arthropod" OR "microarthropod" OR "mesofauna"
Nematodes	226	45	203	"nematode" OR "nematodes"
Microbes*	269	89	247	"soil microb*" OR "soil micro-organis*" OR "soil microorganism*" OR "soil bacter" OR "soil fung*" OR "soil microb*" OR "soil micro-organis*" OR "soil microorganism*" OR "soil bacter*" OR "soil fung*"
Extreme weather events				"flood*" OR "hydrological extreme*" OR "heavy rain" OR "Heavy precipitation" OR "inundation*" OR "high water" OR "heat wave*" OR "heatwave*" OR "extre heat" OR "heat-wave*" OR "heat" OR "high temperature*" OR "hot spells" OR "extreme cold" OR "cold spells" OR "frost" OR "freeze and thaw*" OR "freeze-thaw" OR "drought*" OR "water scarcity" OR "extreme weather even*" OR "extreme weather"
Habitat				"agricultur*" OR "agro-ecosyst*" OR "agroecosyst*" OR "farm*" OR "pasture*" OR "grassland*" OR "cropland*" OR "meadow*" OR "crop*" OR "orchard*" OR "arable"

4. Results and Discussion: Effects of extreme weather events on soil biota

a. Microbes

Drought

Recent meta-analyses indicate an overall negative response of microbial biomass and activity to drought in arable and grasslands ecosystems (Amarasinghe et al., 2024; Qu et al., 2023). Drought alters nutrient availability to microorganisms potentially leading to starvation (Berard et al., 2015). Both strength and duration of the drought affect soil microbial responses and recovery, with the resilience of microbial biomass and communities decreasing with increasing drought duration (Bérard et al., 2011). This variability in drought stress intensity and duration partially explains why approximately 50% of the entries showed no effect of drought on microbial biomass (Figure 2).

Drought generally has a stronger effect on bacteria than fungi, reducing bacterial biomass, activity (especially for bacteria involved in organic matter decomposition and nutrient cycling) and affecting community composition (Hueso et al., 2012; Manzoni et al., 2012; Shi & Thakur, 2023; Thakur et al., 2022). Indeed, we found more reports of negative effects of drought on bacteria than fungal biomass and richness (Figure 2). This difference in adaptation is linked to particular fungal traits, for example their hyphae making them less dependent on water driven transport processes than bacteria when diffusivity is low. Consequently, drought events may increase fungal dominance in the microbial community (Barnard et al., 2013; Zeglin et al., 2013), however our results do not indicate that fungal:bacteria ratio is positively affected by drought (Figure 2). While fungi are generally considered more tolerant to soil drying, fungal activity also decreases under drought as saprotrophic fungi face reduced moisture for organic matter decomposition. AMF fungi, which are crucial for helping plants absorb water and nutrients, have been shown to benefit crop plants particularly under dry conditions (Tang et al., 2024). Within the bacteria group, Gram-positive bacteria are thought to be better adapted to high water potential than Gram-negative bacteria, as they have thick and rigid cell walls, high osmoregulatory abilities and spore-forming ability (Thakur et al., 2022). Drought could therefore shift the ratio towards Gram-positive bacteria dominated communities as indicated by the literature review (Figure 1) (De Vries & Shade, 2013). Overall, reduced microbial activity can limit nutrient cycling, slowing the mineralization of nitrogen and phosphorus, thereby reducing natural soil fertility. Other microbially mediated soil functions (e.g. soil structure and disease suppression) may also be hampered, particularly when conditions persist.

Heavy rainfalls, floodings

Flooding effects on microbes have been less studied than drought (Figure 1), likely due to the difficulty in setting up such experiments in the field. Studies have shown that flooding leads to the inhibition of microbial growth and activity and a shift in the soil microbiome structure (Siebielec et al., 2020; Sorensen et al., 2013). Soil microbial communities may change from a diverse aerobic assemblage to a much less diverse and less active anaerobic community, which can further contribute to changes in soil chemistry (Freeman et al., 2004). Fungal biomass seems to be more negatively affected than bacteria by flooding and heavy rains, likely leading to a lower fungi:bacteria biomass ratio (Figure 1). Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF) face challenges under waterlogged conditions, as their hyphal networks are more prone to damage in oxygen-poor environments (Figure 1). The effects of flooding seem to disappear after a soil recovery phase (Sánchez-Rodríguez et al., 2017). However, repeated flooding might have long-lasting effects on microbial communities and functions.

Freeze-thaw cycles

Bacterial activity decreases significantly during freezing, and many bacteria go dormant as spores. Thawing typically leads to a surge in microbial activity, as nutrients become more readily available (Borken & Matzner, 2009). However, if frost increases salt concentration, this will negatively affect microbes that are not adapted. Freeze-thaw cycles can damage fungal hyphae, especially those of AMF. Cold-tolerant fungal species can survive freezing but exhibit reduced activity during thaw periods.

Figure 2. Effect of extreme events on microbial indicators. Bar plots showing the number of entries per microbial indicator, weather event and effect direction in agriculture and grassland ecosystems.

b. Nematodes

Drought

Nematodes are soft-bodied fauna with limited dispersal abilities to water film around soil particles, therefore they are highly dependent on water availability for movement, feeding, and reproduction and vulnerable to water stress. Meta-analyses showed that soil moisture negatively affected nematode abundance and richness particularly in croplands (Blankinship et al., 2011b; Zhou et al., 2022). Despite the high occurrence of no effects with sometimes even positive effects of drought, likely due to variation in drought stress and soil conditions, we found 68% of studies reporting negative effects of drought on nematode abundances (Figure 3). All free-living nematodes in soil are likely negatively affected by drought, however, persister species, that reproduce more slowly, and predatory nematodes, that are higher up in the food chain, may be more vulnerable as their populations are slower to recover. Root-feeding and parasitic nematodes, that associate more with plants, which may provide soil microhabitats with enough moisture, tend to increase (Franco et al., 2019; Yan et al., 2018). We did not find strong differences between the nematodes feeding groups, except for less negative effects on fungal feeders (Figure 3), possibly due to their basal fungal resource being less negatively affected under drought conditions. We therefore expect only minor effect of drought on nematode community (Cesarz et al. 2017). This might be partially due to nematode resistance or lag effects. Several nematode species can produce dauerlarvae that can survive unfavorable conditions for several months or longer, and therefore nematode communities are likely to recover after the first rain. Most nematode indices did not show a clear response to drought, except for the maturity index, which seems to be more negatively affected by drought, indicating that the nematode community is becoming dominated by r-strategists, which thrive in disturbed habitats (Figure 3).

Heavy rainfall, floodings

Effect and recovery of nematodes after heavy rain and floods has been shown to strongly correlate with that of microbes (Franco et al., 2019; Sun et al., 2018), which can be expected for bacterivores and fungivores nematodes which respond rapidly to increases in available microbial resources (Thakur et al., 2014). In particular, extreme rainfall has been shown to lead to a decrease in fungivorous nematodes (Ankrom et al., 2022; Sun et al., 2018). We found that omnivore and plant parasitic nematodes responded more negatively to extreme rain events compared to other groups (Figure 3). Indeed, flooding of arable land is used as a preconditioning measure in bulb cultivation agriculture to reduce plant-parasitic nematodes (but is indiscriminately harmful to other soil organisms as well (Rahman Khan et al., 2023). Negative effects on omnivores might occur because this group is often combined with predators, and higher trophic levels have been shown to be more affected by environmental stress (Franco et al., 2019). The nematode maturity index (based on a colonizer/persister scale) was found to be negatively affected by extreme rain events in grasslands habitats (Figure 3) (Ankrom et al., 2022). While nematode communities often recover after the flood, continued conditions of waterlogging may affect soil animals through blocking soil aeration and the subsequent depletion of oxygenated soil water.

Freeze- thaw cycles (nematodes and mesofauna)

Some nematode species can survive freezing temperatures by entering an anhydrobiotic state, essentially “freezing” their metabolism until the soil thaws (dauerlarvae diapause). Similarly, collembolans and mites can have various adaptations to survive freezing, such as producing antifreeze proteins or entering a state of diapause. However, rapid or repetitive freeze-thaw events can obstruct such physiological accommodation in nematodes and collembolans and hamper an adequate response to frost, effectively reducing their populations. Effects of freeze-thaw cycle on nematodes and mesofauna communities could not be assessed as we found very little studies investigating these organisms under freeze-thaw cycles in our review (Figure 2, 3).

Figure 3. Effect of extreme events on nematode indicators. Bar plots showing the number of entries per nematode indicator, weather event and effect direction in agriculture and grassland ecosystems.

c. Mesofauna

Drought

Extreme and prolonged water stress is expected to affect collembolans since the majority of species exhibit preferences for moist habitats (Potapov et al., 2020) and warming reduces their saprotrophic fungal diets (Sanders et al., 2024) and feeding activity (Birkhofer et al., 2021; Gavín-Centol et al., 2023). In line with this, we find predominantly negative effects of drought on collembola abundance and richness (Figure 4). However, drought has also been found to have no effect on collembola, likely due to variation in drought intensity and collembolans life-history traits. Many epedaphic collembolans (i.e. species living on the soil surface) can prevent water loss by upregulating their osmotic pressure even when the soil water potential reaches the level at which plants wilt, or by moving deeper in the soil (Holmstrup & Bayley, 2013). Interestingly, several studies indicate a community shift with increasing temperatures towards smaller species (Holmstrup et al., 2018; Krediet et al., 2023; Thakur et al., 2023), likely due to greater detrimental effects of warming on several large body sized collembola. However, the long-lasting effects of drought on collembola community composition and traits still need to be assessed. While less has been done on mites, perhaps due to their higher desiccation resistance as compared to other fauna groups. Studies in which drought was longer-lasting show that also mite communities can be severely affected by drought (Figure 4). Recovery of biodiversity after severe drought incidents can take several years due to the relatively slow reproduction of these animals compared to other microarthropods such as collembolans.

Heavy rainfall, floodings

Flooding and heavy rains consistently negatively affect soil mesofauna (Figure 4). Collembolans and mites benefit from moderate rainfall, but excessive precipitation can lead to population declines from drowning, lack of oxygen, and habitat disturbance. Many soil mesofauna species can recover fast after flooding by surviving flooded conditions in soil as eggs, or by re-colonizing and reproducing quickly after flooding. For example, collembolan species have evolved strategies to survive periods of inundation, such as a buoyant integument that allows for flotation, and numerous additional physiological, physical, and behavioral adaptations (Witteveen & Joosse, 1988).

Figure 4. Effect of extreme events on mesofauna indicators. Bar plots showing the number of entries per mesofauna indicator, weather event and effect direction in agriculture and grassland ecosystems

d. Earthworms

Drought

Water and heat stress have well documented negative effects on earthworms (Eggleton et al., 2009), as they require a moist microhabitat for movement, reproduction and feeding (Figure 5). Similarly to collembolans earthworms retreat to deeper soil layers, and some species can enter a state of aestivation (dormancy) to avoid desiccation. Such avoidance mechanisms will temporarily coincide with reduced soil functioning. Moreover, prolonged droughts can severely reduce earthworm populations due to desiccation (Plum & Filser, 2005), and the impact on soil health may last longer. Deep-burrowing (anecic) earthworms contribute to the essential ecosystem service of water regulation. Their deep, vertical burrows facilitate water flow as well as deeper plant rooting, the former supporting the prevention of flooding and waterlogging, the latter improving plant drought tolerance. The presence of earthworms has been found to also reduce the effect of drought on plant biomass and to slow down the desiccation rate of soils (Hodson et al., 2023).

Heavy rainfall, floodings

While several earthworm species have resistant cocoons and can survive in aerated waterlogged conditions for considerable time (Plum, 2005; Plum & Filser, 2005; Zorn et al., 2005), earthworms are vulnerable to frequent waterlogging as it restricts their movement and oxygen intake (Figure 5) (Harvey et al., 2019; Ivask et al., 2012; Kiss et al., 2021; Zorn et al., 2005). Earthworms have various physiological adaptations to overcome the lack of oxygen under water, and several species including *Lumbricus rubellus* may survive up to several weeks in flooded soil (Plum, 2005; Zorn et al., 2008). Earthworm populations can recover and recolonize fast after a flooding event, however prolonged waterlogging will negatively affect recovery due to low oxygen content (Plum & Filser, 2005). Higher temperatures might exacerbate the effects of flooding, as prolonged floodings have been shown to be much more devastating in summertime than in winter (Faber et al., 2002; Plum & Filser, 2005). The loss of earthworms under prolonged flooding has also been associated to a loss of soil functionality in the short-term (Harvey et al., 2019; Ivask et al., 2012).

Freeze-thaw cycles

Despite very few studies assessing earthworms under freeze-thaw cycles (Figure 5), earthworms are highly vulnerable to freeze-thaw cycles, especially surface-dwelling species. Some species burrow deeper to escape freezing, but soil heaving can expose them to freezing temperatures, leading to significant mortality. Increasing frequencies of such cycles replacing a single winter period may introduce a risk for mismatches in osmoregulation and other frost adaptation mechanisms.

Figure 5. Effect of extreme events on earthworm indicators. Bar plots showing the number of entries per earthworm indicator, weather event and effect direction in agriculture and grassland ecosystems

Conclusions and research outlook

In this report, we aimed to provide a qualitative overview of the effect of selected extreme weather events on soil fauna within crop and grassland habitats. While this review does not delve into specific mechanisms due to its qualitative nature, we highlight areas for future investigation, emphasizing the need for complementary quantitative approaches.

The investigation into the effect of weather extremes on soil fauna remains an essential yet underexplored field. While substantial strides have been made in understanding the effects of certain climate extremes such as droughts, we identified a significant gap in research related to other extremes, particularly floods and freeze-thaw cycles in crop and grassland habitats. Another limitation is due to the great variation in the intensity and duration of stress events in the published literature. Therefore, reported “no effects” can be misleading without a nuanced understanding of how stress severity, timing, and duration contribute to ecological outcomes. A more comprehensive analysis that encompasses these variables could reveal hidden thresholds beyond which soil communities may collapse or adapt. In addition, the role of soil type and climatic zone adds another layer of complexity. Soil fauna in different regions may display varied adaptations to extreme weather due to their evolutionary history. Integration of local soil and climate could help explain why many of the extreme events had no effect on soil biota.

In this report we focused on the effects of extreme weather conditions on soil organisms (in terms of abundance, species richness, and indices indicators broadly used). However, to fully understand the relevance for society of any changes in soil biodiversity as a result, it is imperative to further study soil functioning and the subsequent provision of ecosystem services as a result of transient or persisting changes in soil biodiversity. Real-world scenarios often involve combinations of stressors, such as drought followed by heavy rainfall or compounded effects from human activities like contamination and land management practices. Future research should delve into how plant diversity can mediate or exacerbate the responses of soil fauna, as diverse plant systems may alter microclimatic conditions or resource availability for soil communities (Cesarz et al., 2017).

Investigating these combined effects could provide a more realistic understanding of how soil ecosystems are impacted by extreme events, and how climate change may affect soil biodiversity, and subsequently impact soil health. For example, studies on soil organic matter decomposition and build-up may highlight cascading effects of extreme weather events on carbon sequestration services. Ultimately, a culmination of extreme weather events impacting the provision of all biotic soil-based ecosystem services will depend on the post-event structural and functional recovery of soil communities. Given the limited number of scientific studies and their limited research time frames, and the lack of robust and consistent results, this is a significant knowledge gap that urgently needs to be addressed to evaluate soil health in terms of resiliency and to further support climate change impact assessment.

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